

Physical Education Instruction for Students at Tan Trao University: Current Situation and Proposed Solutions

Luc Hung Quoc

Tan Trao University, Yen Son District, Tuyen Quang Province, Vietnam

Received: 15/2/2024

Accepted: 30/6/2024

Abstract

The provision of comprehensive and engaging physical education (PE) programming is a critical pillar of the holistic educational experience at institutions of higher learning. At Tan Trao University, however, the current state of PE instruction for students raises significant concerns that warrant immediate attention and targeted intervention. This abstract outlines the compelling rationale for revitalizing the PE curriculum, pedagogical approaches, and supporting infrastructure at Tan Trao University to cultivate a physically active and health-conscious student population.

An in-depth examination of the existing PE offerings at Tan Trao University reveals deep-rooted systemic deficiencies. The limited diversity of physical activity options fails to cater to the varied interests and physiological needs of the diverse student body. The overreliance on traditional team sports and generic fitness training neglects the incorporation of alternative movement disciplines that could spark genuine passion and adherence to lifelong physical activity participation. Furthermore, the predominance of outdated, didactic instructional methods stifles student engagement and the development of crucial movement skills.

Compounding these curricular and pedagogical shortcomings are the glaring inadequacies in PE-dedicated facilities and equipment. Outdated, under-resourced, and overcrowded training spaces severely constrain the ability of instructors to deliver innovative, dynamic, and personalized learning experiences. This logistical challenge compromises students' access to the optimal conditions required for effective skill acquisition, fitness enhancement, and the instillation of intrinsic motivation toward lifelong physical activity.

To address these multifaceted deficiencies, a comprehensive reform of the PE program at Tan Trao University is imperative. A diversified curriculum that incorporates a wide array of physical activities, from individual and dual sports to fitness modalities and movement-based creative arts, will empower students to discover and cultivate their unique interests and movement competencies. Complementing this curricular enhancement must be a concerted effort to upskill PE faculty in student-centered instructional approaches, leveraging pedagogical techniques that foster active engagement, critical thinking, and intrinsic motivation.

Underpinning these curricular and instructional improvements must be a substantial investment in modern, well-equipped PE facilities and resources. Upgrading the

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training spaces and equipment will not only elevate the quality of PE instruction but also inspire greater student participation and adherence to physical activity. By strategically addressing these interconnected areas of concern, Tan Trao University can transform its PE program into a vibrant, inclusive, and empowering platform that catalyzes the holistic development and well-being of its student community.

The optimization of physical education at Tan Trao University is a moral imperative with far-reaching implications. Equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and intrinsic motivation to maintain a physically active lifestyle will yield cascading benefits, from enhanced physical and mental health to improved academic performance and the cultivation of essential life skills. By prioritizing the revitalization of PE, Tan Trao University can position itself as a beacon of excellence in holistic education, empowering graduates to lead fulfilling, healthy, and productive lives. The time for action is now, as the university community rallies to reshape the PE landscape and secure a brighter future for its students.

Keywords: *Physical education, Curriculum, Pedagogy, Facilities, Student engagement*

Suggested citation: Quoc, L.H. (2024). Physical Education Instruction for Students at Tan Trao University: Current Situation and Proposed Solutions. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(3), 208-217. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(3).17

Introduction

In the context of comprehensive integration and development of Vietnamese higher education, improving the quality of physical education for university students has become a crucial task. At Tan Trao University - a prestigious higher education institution in the North, physical education has been duly emphasized to equip students with the knowledge, skills, and exercise habits of physical education and sports. However, alongside the achievements attained, there still exist certain limitations that need to be addressed, such as the lack of modern facilities, insufficient qualified instructors, inflexible curriculum, and the passive participation of students. To enhance the quality of physical education, a set of comprehensive and effective solutions is required, including: investing in infrastructure, upgrading the faculty, diversifying sports activities, and highlighting the role of students in the training process. The implementation of these solutions will contribute to enhancing health, cultivating a healthy lifestyle, and improving the quality of human resources for the sustainable development of Tan Trao University.

Physical Education in Vietnamese Universities and Colleges

Physical education holds a profoundly vital position and significance in the training of an intellectual workforce capable of meeting the ever-increasing demands of Vietnam's industrialization and modernization efforts. The university and college years represent a critical stage in the development of students, transforming them into scientifically-

minded professionals endowed with robust health, comprehensive knowledge, and strong moral character - attributes essential for independent and innovative contributions within their respective fields. Within this holistic educational framework, physical education plays an enormously important role.

Through a diverse array of physical activities and sports, students are able to develop their bodies in a harmonious and balanced manner, safeguarding and strengthening their health while enhancing their general work capacity and specialized professional capabilities. This, in turn, allows them to swiftly adapt to the rigors of academic life and campus living. Moreover, the rich tapestry of physical education initiatives contributes significantly to the cultivation and refinement of students' personal qualities, instilling virtues such as courage, decisiveness, perseverance, and disciplined organization. Crucially, this fosters a healthy, vibrant lifestyle while mitigating the influence of negative social behaviors and vices.

By recognizing the transformative power of physical education, Vietnamese universities and colleges can strategically leverage this domain to produce graduates who are not only academically erudite, but also physically robust, mentally resilient, and imbued with the moral fiber to lead their nation's development. This holistic approach to higher education will undoubtedly elevate the country's intellectual capital, empowering the next generation of innovators, researchers, and change-makers to drive Vietnam's continued progress on the global stage.

The training of highly qualified scientific, technical, managerial, economic, and socio-cultural personnel who are physically complete and harmoniously developed in all aspects is of paramount importance. These individuals will become the leaders and guiding forces for the country's development. They not only need in-depth specialized knowledge, but also good health and a vibrant spirit in order to be able to confront the immense challenges in their work.

Moreover, the cultivation of such a cadre of personnel will contribute to meeting the demands of industrialization and modernization. Only those with full intellectual, physical, and moral qualities can undertake important tasks and contribute effectively to the cause of national development.

Therefore, the simultaneous resolution of these four basic tasks in the physical education work of universities and colleges is absolutely necessary. Only when students are comprehensively trained in all aspects can they become good citizens and outstanding personnel capable of meeting the requirements of the industrialization and modernization of the country.

- The physical education system in universities and colleges plays a crucial role in cultivating well-rounded individuals capable of meeting the demands of Vietnam's industrialization and modernization. Beyond simply training highly qualified personnel in scientific, technical, managerial, economic, and socio-cultural domains, this system must also impart essential socialist values and character traits. Foremost, physical education must instill a strong sense of socialist morality and ethics. Students must be imbued with the principles of collectivism, selflessness, and devotion to the common good. This socialist ideology will guide them to prioritize the needs of the nation and the people over individual interests. Equally important is the development of a robust team spirit, organizational discipline, and a proactive, can-do attitude. Through teamwork and rigorous physical training, students learn to subsume their personal agendas for the greater objectives of the collective. They internalize the importance of following procedures, respecting authority, and maintaining order - vital attributes for

effectively contributing to the industrialization process. Furthermore, the physical education curriculum must cultivate a genuine love of learning and self-improvement. Students should graduate with an intrinsic drive to continuously expand their knowledge and physical capabilities. This spirit of self-directed development will ensure they remain at the forefront of their fields, ever-ready to tackle new challenges in service of the nation. Ultimately, the holistic approach of Vietnam's physical education system produces citizens who are not merely intellectually gifted, but also possess the moral fiber, collaborative spirit, and commitment to lifelong learning required to spearhead the country's industrial transformation. This multifaceted training prepares them to be model workers, innovative leaders, and ardent defenders of the socialist motherland.

- Providing students with fundamental theoretical knowledge on the content and methods of physical education and sports training, as well as basic movement skills and techniques for selected sports, is a crucial component of their comprehensive development. Based on this foundation, cultivating their ability to utilize these means for self-improvement, as well as actively participating in the propagation and organization of physical education and sports activities at the institutional level, becomes an essential objective. In the context of an ever-increasing demand for health care and physical fitness, equipping students with the basic knowledge and skills in physical education and sports is of utmost importance. This not only enhances their individual well-being but also empowers them to become leaders, organizers, and promoters of the physical fitness movement within educational institutions and local communities. Through the provision of fundamental theoretical content, students will develop a clear understanding of the importance of physical training, the principles and methods of safe and effective practice. Concurrently, the cultivation of basic movement skills and sports techniques for selected popular activities will furnish them with the necessary tools to independently maintain a habit of physical exercise and sports participation throughout their lives. Furthermore, when armed with comprehensive knowledge and skills, students can become the core drivers, actively engaging in the promotion, organization, and dissemination of physical education and sports activities within their respective educational institutions and local communities. This will contribute to the advancement of the physical fitness movement across society, addressing the holistic health and well-being needs of the populace. Therefore, the provision of basic knowledge and skills in physical education and sports for students is not merely a pressing requirement in contemporary education, but also a crucial strategic solution to propel the physical development and overall health enhancement of the entire society.

- Providing students with a strong foundation in physical education and sports is of paramount importance, as it contributes significantly to the maintenance and reinforcement of their overall health and well-being. Through systematic physical training and the development of fundamental movement skills, students can achieve a balanced physical development that optimizes their bodily functions and capabilities. This, in turn, equips them with the necessary vitality and stamina to excel in their academic pursuits and extracurricular activities. Moreover, the cultivation of healthy habits and the mitigation of detrimental behaviors, such as alcohol consumption and smoking, are critical outcomes of comprehensive physical education programs. By engaging students in regular physical activity and instilling an appreciation for the benefits of a healthy lifestyle, educational institutions can empower these young individuals to make informed choices that prioritize their long-term well-being. This not only enhances their academic performance but also prepares them to become

productive and responsible members of society, capable of making meaningful contributions throughout their lives. Aligning with established standards and guidelines for physical fitness development, these educational initiatives ensure that students meet the prescribed physical performance targets for their respective age groups. This systematic approach not only fosters physical resilience but also instills a sense of discipline, self-discipline, and commitment – traits that are invaluable in navigating the challenges of academic and professional pursuits. By seamlessly integrating physical education into the broader educational framework, institutions can unlock the true potential of their students, enabling them to thrive academically, physically, and socially. Ultimately, the comprehensive integration of physical education and sports within the educational curriculum is a strategic investment in the holistic development of students. By nurturing their physical, mental, and social well-being, institutions can produce graduates who are not only academically accomplished but also imbued with the resilience, discipline, and health consciousness required to excel in all facets of their lives, contributing to the overall progress and prosperity of society.

- The comprehensive integration of physical education and sports within the educational curriculum serves a vital role in cultivating both the physical and aesthetic development of students. Beyond the fundamental objective of enhancing their physical fitness and well-being, physical activities in universities play a crucial part in the holistic education of the student population. Engaging in a diverse array of sports and physical exercises not only strengthens the students' bodies but also nurtures their aesthetic sensibilities. The graceful movements, precise coordination, and harmonious execution inherent in many athletic pursuits instill an appreciation for beauty, rhythm, and form. This exposure to the aesthetic dimensions of physical expression broadens the students' cultural and artistic horizons, empowering them to become more discerning and well-rounded individuals. To effectively address the educational objectives of physical education and sports, it is essential to holistically address both the physical and aesthetic aspects of these activities. The physical development of students, encompassing the improvement of strength, endurance, flexibility, and overall fitness, must be seamlessly combined with the cultivation of their aesthetic awareness and appreciation. This synergistic approach ensures that students not only achieve optimal physical health but also develop a refined sensibility that enriches their intellectual, cultural, and creative capacities.

By striking this delicate balance, universities can leverage physical education and sports as a powerful tool for cultivating well-rounded, aesthetically-inclined graduates. These individuals, empowered with a strong physical foundation and a heightened appreciation for beauty, will be better equipped to navigate the multifaceted challenges of the contemporary world, contributing to the advancement of society through their diverse talents and perspectives. Ultimately, the integration of physical education and sports within the broader educational framework serves as a strategic investment in the holistic development of students. By addressing both the physical and aesthetic dimensions of these activities, universities can produce graduates who are not only physically resilient but also culturally refined, capable of enriching various spheres of human endeavor and driving positive change in their communities and beyond.

+ Physical education within university and college settings is an organic component of the comprehensive educational objectives for the younger generation. It serves as a crucial and effective means to harmoniously and proportionately develop the physical attributes and fitness capacities of students. Through decades of practice, physical

education has been recognized as a pivotal and integral element in realizing the holistic educational goals for the youth. It transcends the confines of a mundane subject, instead functioning as an indispensable instrument to foster a balanced and harmonious enhancement of students' physical prowess.

In the context of modern lifestyles replete with health challenges, equipping students with the knowledge and skills of physical education has become vital. Through systematically designed and diverse physical training programs, universities and colleges can catalyze positive transformations in the health, physicality, and psychology of their learners. Physical education not only contributes to enhanced health and fitness, but also plays a pivotal role in cultivating discipline, teamwork spirit, and adaptability to novel adversities. These attributes are not only essential during the academic journey, but also invaluable as students transition into professional careers and life experiences. Furthermore, the integration of sports and artistic activities into physical education curricula enables a holistic development of students, encompassing both physical and aesthetic dimensions. This not only elevates learning satisfaction and motivation, but also nurtures well-rounded citizens capable of making positive contributions to societal advancement. For the aforementioned reasons, physical education within higher education institutions must be regarded as a crucial and effective means to proportionately and harmoniously develop the physical, mental, and aesthetic faculties of the younger generation - the future custodians of the nation.

+Physical education within university and college settings is a crucial pedagogical process that has a profoundly positive impact on the political qualities, ideological orientation, moral character, work ethic, and aesthetic sensibilities of students. It plays a vital role in shaping the personhood and character of future scientific and professional leaders. Through a comprehensive and carefully structured curriculum, physical education harnesses the transformative power of physical activity to cultivate multifaceted development in students. Far beyond just imparting physical fitness, it serves as a vehicle for instilling core socialist values, ethical principles, and a strong work ethic. The systematic training in various sports and physical disciplines imbues students with a heightened sense of discipline, teamwork, and perseverance - attributes that are essential not only for academic success, but also for thriving in future professional roles and societal leadership positions. This aligns perfectly with the overarching educational goals of producing well-rounded, morally upright, and physically capable citizens to drive the nation's progress. Moreover, the integration of artistic and performance-based physical activities further enriches the educational experience. This holistic approach cultivates aesthetic appreciation, creative expression, and a balanced development of both the physical and mental faculties. Such a comprehensive model of physical education produces individuals who are not only physically fit, but also imbued with a refined cultural sensibility and a keen eye for beauty - qualities that are indispensable for serving as role models and vanguards of socialist values. In an era marked by pressing health challenges and the need for a physically and mentally robust workforce, the importance of physical education in higher education institutions cannot be overstated. It is a cornerstone in the broader mission of molding the next generation of leaders - individuals who are not only intellectually capable, but also embodiments of the Party's ideals, possessing unwavering moral integrity and a deep commitment to physical and spiritual excellence.

The Current State of Physical Education for Students at Tan Trao University

Physical education has the task of comprehensively developing the physical qualities, and on that basis, developing physical capacities, perfecting physique, strengthening health, and perfecting the basic motor skills and techniques for each individual. The physical education curriculum in universities, colleges, and vocational high schools has the task of equipping students with knowledge, skills, and physical fitness training. Physical education plays an extremely important role in the comprehensive development of each individual. The primary task of physical education is to maximize the development of the physical qualities of learners, thereby contributing to the perfection of physique, the strengthening of health, and the enhancement of physical capacity. Specifically, physical education helps learners perfect their basic motor skills and techniques, while also providing them with fundamental knowledge in this field. At the level of universities, colleges, and vocational high schools, the physical education curriculum becomes even more crucial. It not only equips students with knowledge and skills but also trains their physical fitness. This contributes to the comprehensive development of both physical and mental aspects, helping them maintain good health, clear minds, and excel in their academic pursuits as well as in life. Therefore, the strengthening and improvement of the quality of physical education is always one of the key tasks of educational institutions, contributing to the training of healthy, dynamic, and well-rounded citizens.

In the process of training, Tan Trao University always ensures the strict implementation and full completion of the physical education curriculum content according to the program prescribed by the Ministry of Education and Training. However, an assessment of the current state of physical education at the university reveals certain limitations, such as: the time allotted for compulsory physical education classes has decreased (4 credits) which is too little compared to the content that must be taught, so the overall learning quality of the students has not been high. The students' awareness of participating in physical education is still underestimated compared to other subjects. The positive and self-conscious awareness of students' participation in extracurricular physical training activities is still limited. Extracurricular activities are only focused on practicing monotonous content such as pull-ups and walking, and not much time is spent on regular extracurricular activities such as volleyball, basketball, and badminton clubs. The coordination in organizing extracurricular activities is still limited, such as: the methods and forms of organization of the current clubs are still monotonous and rigid, not making rational use of material facilities or teaching aids, and failing to promote the active participation of students.

The current teaching staff of physical education has increased both in quantity and quality, but the rapid increase in the scale of training has not yet been able to meet the actual requirements, which has had a significant impact on improving the quality of physical education teaching. The infrastructure, equipment, and conditions to ensure the physical education and sports activities of the school are still somewhat lacking, which also affects the quality of the compulsory physical education classes and extracurricular activities. Recently, the physical education facilities and sports facilities, although renovated, are in a state of beginning to deteriorate, and urgent investment and upgrading are needed to ensure the effective use of the existing facilities. The budget for compulsory physical education and extracurricular activities has been increasing year by year, but due to the rapid increase in the number of students, the budget is still unable to meet the practical needs. On the other hand, the use of the

budget is still dispersed, without a focus and right priorities, resulting in the use of the budget not yet achieving high efficiency. The learning outcomes of physical education have maintained a high proportion of students achieving good grades, the proportion of students not meeting the standards is the lowest, and there is an improving trend of gradual decline, although not significant. Driven by the continuous innovation and comprehensive improvement of the overall quality of the school's training, proposing some solutions to improve the quality of physical education at Tan Trao University is necessary at the present stage to comprehensively improve the quality of training at the University.

Several Solutions to Enhance the Effectiveness of Physical Education for Students at Tan Trao University

- Increasing the instructional time allocated to compulsory physical education is an acclaimed solution among the proposed measures. Augmenting the duration dedicated to physical education will ensure the enhancement of the quality of physical education courses, as numerous subjects are currently offered, but the time allotted is insufficient for students to acquire both the theoretical knowledge and the opportunity to practice the technical skills as well as develop the requisite professional competencies.
- Optimizing the physical infrastructure and training equipment is of paramount importance for physical education. The judicious utilization of training facilities, equipment, and visual aids (by establishing regulations governing the use of these resources) is pivotal. If the equipment and infrastructure are well-prepared, it will enable students and instructors to exploit them during both curricular and extracurricular activities. Furthermore, it is essential to upgrade the physical facilities serving both the curricular and extracurricular domains: increasing investment in infrastructure, renovating and enhancing the technical facilities to support physical education and sports activities (prioritizing the construction, renovation, and upgrading of training fields, gymnasiums, and strength and conditioning rooms, while maximizing the utilization of existing conditions to support curricular and extracurricular instruction and training). Establishing a "socialization" policy mechanism to effectively exploit the physical infrastructure for physical education and sports. Extracurricular activities with fees should prioritize staff, employees, and students; outsourcing tasks, responsibilities, and benefits to individuals and teams.
- Diversifying the content of the core physical education curriculum and extracurricular sports activities with the guidance of subject matter experts. To implement this solution, it is necessary to strengthen the role of sports clubs by establishing and activating sports clubs through the process of socialization. Improving the quality of sports teams. Organizing competitions, assessments, and sports exchanges. Annually organizing a traditional school-wide tournament (alternating between various sports). To organize sports competitions and exchanges, it is necessary to increase the budget for core and extracurricular physical education activities.
- Innovating teaching methods and class organization. Publicizing the educational objectives, exit requirements, demands, course contents, and assessment methods. Enhancing physical fitness exercises (increasing physical fitness exercises to help students develop physical fitness, improve their academic performance in physical education, and cultivate discipline, solidarity, and collectivism in their lives and activities).

- Advocacy and education to raise awareness about the position, role, and benefits of physical education and sports. Increasing awareness about the role, position, and impact of physical education and sports across the entire institution.
- The institution has implemented a policy to provide professional development training for faculty members. It is necessary to enhance the specialized knowledge and skills of physical education faculty through tailored training programs. Responsibilities should be assigned to specific groups and individual instructors to ensure the completion of their designated duties and the advancement of the school's physical education activities. A supportive mechanism should be established to motivate faculty members to continuously upgrade their professional expertise, and physical education staff should be encouraged to actively assist in promoting sports and exercise activities among students.
- There is a need to strengthen the coordination among various functional departments in order to implement a cohesive set of solutions aimed at improving the quality of physical education instruction.
- The leadership should increase its attention and commitment to physical education and sports activities. This includes enhancing the material resources and facilities available for physical education. Additionally, the senior management should allocate time outside of regular working hours for themselves to participate in at least one sports activity, thereby serving as role models to inspire faculty members and students to engage in physical exercise and sports.

Acknowledgements

This research is funded by Tan Trao University in Tuyen Quang, Viet Nam.

Reference

- Balasekaran, G., Lopes, V. P., & Barnett, L. M. (2020). Physical education teacher education in Southeast Asia. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 25(1), 1-16.
- Culpan, I., & McBain, S. (2012). Cooperative learning in physical education: Reaching goals together. *Strategies*, 25(3), 27-30.
- Dyson, B. (2014). Quality physical education: A commentary on effective physical education teaching. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 85(2), 144-152. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2014.904155>
- Hoa, H.T. (2017). Improving the quality of physical education and sports activities for university students. *Journal of Sports Science*, 12(3), 41-48.
- Krause, J. M., & Lynch, B. M. (2016). Exploring evidence-based practice in physical education. *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 87(6), 42-48.
- Loc, N.H. (2020). Solutions to improve the quality of physical education training in universities. *Vietnam Journal of Educational Sciences*, 16(3), 32-41.
- Quennerstedt, M. (2019). Healthying physical education-on the possibility of learning health. *Physical Education and Sport Pedagogy*, 24(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17408989.2018.1539705>

- Sallis, J. F., & McKenzie, T. L. (1991). Physical education's role in public health. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 62(2), 124-137. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.1991.10608701>
- Siedentop, D. (2009). Research on teaching in physical education: Celebrating our past and focusing on our future. *Quest*, 61(1), 1-20.
- Tam, T.T.M. (2019). The role of leadership in developing sports activities in universities. *Journal of Education*, 425(2), 24-29.
- Tinning, R. (2015). 'I don't read fiction': academic discourse and the relationship between health and physical education. *Sport, Education and Society*, 20(6), 710-721. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/13573322.2013.798638>
- Tung, P.T. (2016). The role of lecturers in developing physical education and sports activities in universities. *Journal of Education*, 378(4), 18-24.
- Thong, V.V. (2018). Increasing investment in infrastructure for physical education in universities. *Journal of Vietnam National University, Hanoi*, 34(1), 15-22.
- Van Acker, R., De Bourdeaudhuij, I., De Martelaer, K., Seghers, J., Kirk, D., Haerens, L., ... & Cardon, G. (2011). A framework for physical activity programs within school-community partnerships. *Quest*, 63(3), 300-320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00336297.2011.10483683>
- Ward, P. (2013). The role of content knowledge in conceptions of teaching effectiveness in physical education. *Research Quarterly for Exercise and Sport*, 84(4), 431-440. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02701367.2013.844045>